

Graphical Abstract

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Abstract

Carbon dioxide hydrates are ice-like nonstoichiometric inclusion solid compounds with importance to global climate change, and gas transportation and storage. The thermodynamic and kinetic mechanisms that control carbon dioxide nucleation critically depend on hydrate-water interfacial free energy. Only two independent indirect experiments are available in the literature. Interfacial energies show large uncertainties and overestimated values due to the conditions at which experiments are performed. Under these circumstances, computer simulation tools offer a way to estimate interfacial energies at coexistence conditions from a molecular perspective. We propose a novel implementation of a computational methodology based on the definition of interfacial energy and the use of realistic and reliable models of water (TIP4P/Ice) and carbon dioxide (TraPPE) that have proven to predict accurately the ice-water interfacial energy and the dissociation line of carbon dioxide hydrates. We found that simulations provide an interfacial energy value, at coexistence conditions, consistent with the experiments from its thermodynamic definition.

Keywords:

Interfacial free energy, carbon dioxide hydrate, hydrate-water interface, computer simulation

1. Introduction

Hydrates are nonstoichiometric inclusion solid compounds in which guest molecules, such as methane (CH₄), carbon dioxide (CO₂) and molecular hydrogen (H₂), among many others species, are enclathrated in the voids left by a periodic network of water molecules (host) [1]. Hydrates of small molecules, such as CH₄, CO₂ and H₂ form sI hydrates [1], while larger substances usually form sII and sH hydrate structures [2, 3]. Fundamental and applied research on hydrates has been motivated by several reasons. From an applied point of view, hydrates are potential alternative sources of energy as CH₄ hydrate deposits [4, 5], and also are important from their global climate impact [1–6], CO₂ sequestration [7–9] and gas storage [10] and transportation [11–13].

From a more general and fundamental point of view, the mechanisms that control the thermodynamics and growth kinetics of these materials are still poorly under-

stood [1, 14]. The precise knowledge of these parameters is essential to understand, from a molecular perspective, the growth patterns and nucleation, and particularly interfacial free energies of these strategic materials [15]. In this work we concentrate on the determination of interfacial free energies of type sI hydrates, and particularly on the CO₂ hydrate-water interfacial free energy.

Although there exist well established and reliable methods in the literature for the experimental determination of fluid-fluid (FF) interfacial tensions [16, 17], the situation is not as optimistic in the case of solid-fluid (SF) interfaces. There is a rather limited number of methods for obtaining experimental free energies from experiments or theoretical calculations [15].

Experimental data consists of indirect measurements combining the difference between the melting or dissociation temperature in pore and that in bulk of hydrates and the Gibbs-Thomson relationship [18–20]. The method is based on the measurement, at constant pressure, of the dissociation/formation of a hydrate inside porous materials with a given mean pore diameter, as indicated in part (a) of Scheme 1. The tempera-

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Scheme 1: Methods for determining hydrate-water interfacial energies: (a) experiments and use of the Gibbs-Thomson (GT) equation; (b) computer simulation combined with Classical Nucleation Theory (CNT); (c) Mold Integration methodology proposed in this work.

ture at which this happens depends on the pore diameter and is different from that in bulk phase. The relative difference between both temperatures is given in terms of different magnitudes, including the interfacial free energy of the CO_2 hydrate-water interface through the Gibbs-Thomson equation. The most important approximations of this approach are the capillary approximation and that all pores in the porous materials are cylindrical, with only one and well-defined pore size, independent, and nonconnected pores. Unfortunately, real mesoporous materials are far from this idyllic picture. They are made by a network of interconnected cylindrical pores with a given pore size distribution. This produces a combination of “individual” experimental dissociation curves and different definitions for the mean pore diameter, provoking large discrepancies between interfacial energy values found in the literature. To the best of our knowledge, Uchida *et al.* [21, 22] and Anderson *et al.* [23, 24] were the first and only authors that measured the interfacial free energies of CO_2 hydrates using this indirect method, obtaining 28(6) and 30(3) mJ/m^2 , respectively. Other authors have also stud-

ied the effect of different porous media on equilibrium pressure of several hydrates [25–32]. Note that although error bars of both indirect experimental values make the data compatible, the uncertainties are large, especially in the case of Uchida’s measures.

When experimental values are scarce or it is necessary to assess experimental measures of some magnitudes, as in the case of the hydrate-water interfacial free energy, computer simulations of realistic models constitute a valuable and efficient alternative method that can also improve our understanding on the hydrate-water interface from a molecular perspective [33, 34]. Although a number of simulation methodologies to calculate SF interfacial free energies exists in the literature [35–38], all of them are usually efficient for simple molecular models and not all of them are accurate, simple, and cheap from the point of view of the computational cost for complex solid structures. It is important to note that Davidchack and collaborators have determined, not only the interfacial free energy of hard-spheres [39, 40] and Lennard-Jones [41] systems using the Cleaving method, but also for several models of water [42, 43].

Several authors have determined the dissociation line of the CO_2 hydrates using computer simulation, including Míguez *et al.* [44], as well as Constandy and collaborators [45], and Waage *et al.* [46]. However, the CO_2 hydrate interfacial free energy has not been previously calculated from computer simulation at coexistence conditions. Molinero and coworkers [47, 48] have estimated indirectly the interfacial free energy of the CH_4 combining simulation and the methodologies (a) and (b) in Scheme 1. However, this theory assumes that interfacial energy of small clusters is equal to that of a macroscopic solid-liquid planar interface. This approximation, the so-called capillarity approximation, affects the interfacial energy values obtained from this methodology. Other authors simulate the CH_4 hydrate and use the mechanical definition of the interfacial tension [49–51]. However, this methodology does not provide reliable free energy values since the mechanical route does not account for interfacial energies in solid phases.

Here, we propose a novel implementation of the Mold Integration (MI) methodology proposed by Vega and collaborators [52] to deal with SF interfaces of CO_2 hydrates and water, as indicated in part (c) of Scheme 1. The technique used in this work is based only on the thermodynamic definition of interfacial energy and on the use of standard local-order parameters. Calculation of the interfacial free energy is evaluated using a mold of attractive sites to induce reversibly the formation of a solid CO_2 hydrate slab, as indicated in part

(c) of Scheme 1. The technique, implemented using molecular dynamics simulations, is simple and allows to predict interfacial free energies from a fundamental point of view. The final aim of this work is to predict the CO₂ hydrate-water interfacial free energy at coexistence conditions combining this methodology with realistic and widely used water and CO₂ molecular models: the TIP4P/ice [53] and TraPPE [54], respectively. It is important to remark two points: (1) the TIP4P/ice model is able to predict accurately the ice-water interfacial free energy [52] and both models are able to quantitatively predict the three-phase or dissociation line of the CO₂ hydrate [44].

It is important to mention that classical force fields for H₂O + CO₂ mixture are very limited. Particularly, these models do not account for many-body contributions in polar compounds, and consequently, do not describe polarization and other electrostatic effects. During last years, several authors have described this issue [55, 56] and more sophisticated models including three-body interactions [57] and the use of many body TTM-rng and MB-rng potential energy functions developed by Paesani and coworkers [57, 58], have been proposed. However, the use of more rigorous and detailed models requires the correct description of the CO₂ hydrate dissociation line and will probably multiply the CPU time by a non-negligible factor. The main goal of this work is to show that it is possible to determine interfacial energies of hydrates from computer simulation and first principles. From this point of view, the election of a simple but enough accurate model that can be simulated using reasonably CPU resources is justified.

The novelty of our work with respect to previous results is that we obtain the interfacial free energy of a very complex and interesting mixture from both practical and fundamental point of views. This is done at coexistence conditions, from fundamental principles, including the definition of interfacial free energy and well-established tools from Thermodynamics and Statistical Mechanics.

2. Methodology

In this work, we use the MI methodology to determine the interfacial free energy between the CO₂ hydrate crystalline solid and the aqueous solution of CO₂ at coexistence conditions. According to this, the work needed to form a thin crystalline slab of hydrate in the aqueous solution, ΔG^{hw} , is directly related with the hydrate-water interfacial free energy, γ_{hw} , through its definition,

$$\gamma_{hw} = \frac{\Delta G^{hw}}{2\mathcal{A}} \quad (1)$$

Here \mathcal{A} is the area of the interface between the hydrate and the aqueous solution of CO₂ and the factor 2 arises because once the crystalline solid slab is created there are two hydrate-water interfaces. It is important to remark that Eq. (1) only holds if ΔG^{hw} , the reversible work needed to induce the formation of a hydrate slab, is determined at coexistence conditions. These means that all phases in contact have the same chemical potential, i.e., the CO₂ hydrate solid phase and the two liquid phases coexist at the same temperature and pressure.

Homogeneous nucleation of any crystalline solid phase from its liquid, including hydrates, is an activated process [14, 59, 60]. Typically, times and lengths at which nucleation occurs are in the nanoseconds and in the nanometers time and length scales, respectively [1, 14]. This is why homogeneous nucleation is considered a rare event, which means that it is nearly impossible to observe spontaneously, experimentally or by means of molecular simulation, the growth of a solid phase from its liquid [1, 14].

To overcome this problem and induce the formation of the hydrate crystal slab, we place attractive interaction sites in the H₂O-rich liquid phase at the equilibrium positions of the oxygen atoms of water in one of principal planes of the sI structure of the CO₂ hydrate. The particular number and positions occupied by the attractive interaction sites are described in the next Section. The most appropriate intermolecular potential to act as catalyst of the hydrate slab is a continuous version of the square-well potential [60] characterized by two molecular parameters: the range of interaction, r_w , and the well depth, ε . See the works of Espinosa *et al.* [52, 60, 61] for further details on the particular implementation of this continuous square-well intermolecular potential. This mold of attractive sites provokes attractive interactions between them and water molecules. In other words, when the mold is switched off, water molecules can diffuse freely in the fluid. However, as the mold is progressively switched on (increasing the well depth, ε , from 0 to a maximum value, ε_m), an increasing number of sites of the mold are occupied by water molecules. If r_w , the attractive interaction range of the wells, is sufficiently narrow a CO₂ hydrate crystal slab is formed around the positions of the mold wells. Note that this parameter must be small enough to accommodate only one water molecule when the wells are switched on. This methodology has been proposed and used successfully by Espinosa *et al.* to determine accurately the interfacial free energy of the Lennard-Jones

and hard-sphere systems [60], sodium chloride [61], and several models of water [52] at coexistence conditions.

The free energy difference between the fluid and the fluid with the mold fully occupied, ΔG_m , can be obtained using a thermodynamic integration along a path in which the attractive interaction between the mold sites and water molecules, ε , is gradually switched from the state in which the interaction is switched off, $\varepsilon = 0$ (all water molecules in fluid phase) to another in which the mold sites are fully switched on, $\varepsilon = \varepsilon_m$ (some water molecules form a hydrate slab). ΔG_m can be written as, [52].

$$\Delta G_m = - \int_0^{\varepsilon_m} \langle N_{fw}(\varepsilon) \rangle_{NP_z\mathcal{A}T} d\varepsilon \quad (2)$$

where $\langle N_{fw}(\varepsilon) \rangle_{NP_z\mathcal{A}T}$ is the number of filled wells averaged over the configurations generated using the isothermal-isobaric or $NP_z\mathcal{A}T$ ensemble when the interaction energy is ε . Here P_z and T are the coexistence pressure and temperature, respectively. ΔG^{hw} is calculated subtracting the contribution that represents the interaction energy between the water molecules and the mold, $-N_w\varepsilon_m$.

$$\Delta G^{hw} = N_w\varepsilon_m + \Delta G_m \quad (3)$$

Here N_w is the total number of wells. The contribution $-N_w\varepsilon_m$ represents the interaction energy between the water molecules and the mold and must be subtracted from ΔG_m to obtain the reversible work to form the crystalline slab [61]. The value of ε_m must satisfy two conditions: (1) it should be high enough to guarantee that every well of the mold is occupied by a water molecule in the final state of the integration path; and (2) ε_m should be low enough to ensure that integrand of Eq. (2) behaves smoothly when ε varies from 0 to ε_m . Large values of ε_m produce large variations of $\langle N_{fw}(\varepsilon) \rangle_{NP_z\mathcal{A}T}$ and a large number of intermediate states must be used to ensure an accurate determination of the interfacial free energy. In this work, we have used $\varepsilon_m = 8 k_B T$, where k_B is the Boltzmann constant and T the temperature of the system. This value allows to ensure that all sites of the mold are filled by water molecules for values of $\varepsilon < \varepsilon_m$ [52, 60].

The calculation of ΔG^{hw} following Eqs. (2) and (3) can be used to determine the CO₂ hydrate-water interfacial free energy only if it represents the reversible work to induce the formation of a hydrate slab. Hence, one must ensure that the system does not cross a first-order phase transition along the integration path. In other words, in all the states chosen to perform the thermodynamics integration the system cannot fully form a solid

crystalline (hydrate) phase. According to Espinosa *et al.* [61], this is practically done using potential ranges, r_w , wider than a certain optimal range value, r_w^0 . A full explanation on how r_w^0 is determined in this work is explained in the Results and discussion Section.

3. Simulation details

The method for calculating the SF interfacial free energy involves four steps: (1) preparation of the simulation box with the fluid phases that coexist at thermodynamic conditions at which the interfacial free energy is obtained; (2) determination of the optimal well radius r_w^0 ; (3) calculation of the SF interfacial free energy as a function of the well radius r_w using thermodynamic integration; and (4) extrapolation of the interfacial free energy to r_w^0 . In this section, we concentrate in step (1). Steps (2)-(4) are presented in the next Sections.

Contrary to what happens in pure systems [52, 60], the use of the MI technique for hydrates requires special attention because the coexistence conditions of the hydrate-water interface involves two different components (H₂O and CO₂) and three phases in equilibrium, the CO₂ hydrate solid, H₂O-rich liquid, and CO₂-rich liquid phases. We use the phase diagram of the CO₂ hydrate recently determined by some of us [44], combining the well-known direct coexistence technique, the TIP4P/Ice model for water [53], and the TraPPE model for CO₂ [54], to select the conditions at which all simulations are performed in this work: 40 MPa and 287 K. According to Figure 1, these conditions (filled green square) correspond to a state point along the dissociation line of the CO₂ hydrate. Note that the vapor phase only exists at temperatures and pressure below the vapor-liquid coexistence curve of pure CO₂ (blue continuous curve).

Although there are experimental values [62, 63] of the precise location of the three-phase line at a wide range of pressures, we only concentrate in this work on the interfacial free energy of the CO₂ hydrate-water interface at 40 MPa and 287 K. These conditions are selected because agreement between experimental data taken from the literature and computer simulation predictions for coexistence is excellent. In addition to that, and according to the available experimental data from Uchida [21, 22] and Anderson [23, 24], γ_{hw} is independent of temperature and pressure along the three-phase dissociation line of CO₂ hydrates.

We perform MD simulations in combination with the direct coexistence technique in the isothermal-isobaric or $NP_z\mathcal{A}T$ ensemble [64, 65]. We use a parallelepiped simulation box of volume $V = L_x \times L_y \times L_z$, where L_x , L_y ,

Figure 1: Pressure-temperature projection of the three-phase coexistence line (CO₂ hydrate – H₂O – CO₂) of the CO₂ hydrate. Red circles represent the experimental data taken from the literature [62], the blue curve the experimental vapor pressure of pure CO₂ [63], and the green squares the results obtained by Míguez *et al.* [44] from molecular dynamics simulation using the direct coexistence technique. H corresponds to the hydrate phase, L₁ and L₂ represent the CO₂-rich and H₂O-rich liquid phases, respectively, and V is the vapor. The filled green square represents the state point (287 K and 40 MPa) at which simulations are performed in this work.

and L_z are the dimensions of the simulation box. L_x and L_y are kept constant and only L_z is varied along the simulation. This ensures that system is under the equilibrium normal pressure (perpendicular to the hydrate slab formed when the mold is switched on). It also avoids stress in the system, keeping L_x and L_y constants and consistent with the equilibrium unit cell of the hydrate phase at coexistence conditions.

To prepare the simulation box used in this work, we first consider two homogeneous liquid systems, a pure water liquid phase formed by 736 molecules of water and two pure CO₂ liquid phases formed by 128 CO₂ molecules each of them. Dimensions of the initial simulation boxes are chosen to be consistent with the size of the hydrate unit cell along the x - and y -axis that will be formed when the mold is switched on. According to this, $L_x = L_y = 24 \text{ \AA}$ and kept fixed during all the simulations. We also place $N_w = 56$ attractive interaction sites at the equilibrium positions of the oxygen atoms of water located at one of the principal planes of the sl structure of the CO₂ hydrate. We recommend to see Figure 1 of our previous work [44] to identify the particular positions of the oxygen atoms at which the mold sites are placed. Note that the sites are switch off during the setup of the simulation box. They are only switched

on when the MI method is used, as it is explained in the next section. After this, the final simulation box is built linking up the three bulk boxes forming a CO₂-rich liquid - H₂O-rich liquid - CO₂-rich liquid or L₁ – L₂ – L₁ system. The liquid-liquid (LL) system is equilibrated along 5 ns. After this, the equilibrium value of the length of the simulation box along the z -axis was $L_z \approx 66.5 \text{ \AA}$.

We use a Verlet leapfrog algorithm [66] with a time step of 0.0015 ns to solve the Newton’s equations. All simulations are run at constant temperature and pressure using a Nosé-Hoover thermostat [67] and an anisotropic Parrinello-Rahman barostat [68]. Relaxation times used in the thermostat and barostat are 2 and 1 ps, respectively. Long-range interactions due to electrostatic interactions are determined using the Particle Mesh Ewald technique [69]. We use a cutoff radius for both dispersive interactions and the real part of electrostatic interactions of 10 \AA . The final simulation box obtained as explained above has been used as initial simulation box in the rest of the work to determine the optimal value of the attractive interaction range of the wells, r_w^0 , and to calculate the number of filled wells for different values of r_w and ε .

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Determination of r_w^0

We have checked, following the works of Espinosa *et al.* [52, 60, 61], that it is possible to induce a CO₂ hydrate slab using a mold with appropriate values of r_w and ε , the well radius and depth of the mold, respectively. As it is discussed previously, ε values in the range $0 < \varepsilon \leq \varepsilon_m$, with $\varepsilon_m = 8k_B T$, once the mold is switched on, allow the water molecules to occupy all the sites of the mold, promoting the growth of the CO₂ hydrate slab. To check this, we have used first a mold of attractive sites with a very low value of $r_w = 0.760 \text{ \AA}$ and $\varepsilon = \varepsilon_m = 8k_B T$. As we will see later in this section, very low values of r_w are not appropriate for calculating interfacial free energies. However, this election of parameters is useful at this level for checking if the mold is really able to induce the formation of a CO₂ hydrate phase.

Figure 2 shows three snapshots extracted from MD trajectories of the simulation prepared as explained in the previous Section (LL interfacial system for the CO₂ + H₂O system), with the mold switched on ($r_w = 0.760 \text{ \AA}$ and $\varepsilon = 8k_B T$). As can be seen, at $t = 0 \text{ ns}$ (top) the system exhibits LL immiscibility, with a H₂O-rich liquid phase (center of the simulation box) in coexistence with a CO₂-rich liquid phase (left and right of the

Figure 2: Snapshots showing the crystallization of the CO₂ hydrate phase from the water-CO₂ two-phase coexistence at 40 MPa and 287 K. Different parts show the simulation box for (top) $t = 0$, (middle) $t = 50$ ns, and (bottom) $t = 200$ ns. Red and white licorice representation corresponds to oxygen and hydrogen atoms of water, respectively, yellow and blue spheres (Van der Waals representation) correspond to carbon and oxygen atoms of CO₂, respectively, and green spheres (Van der Waals representation) correspond to the mold attractive sites with $r_w = 0.760$ Å and $\varepsilon = 8 k_B T$.

simulation box). The attractive sites of the mold (green spheres) occupy the equilibrium positions of the oxygen atoms of water of one lattice plane of the CO₂ hydrate. 50 ns later (middle), water molecules have arranged around the equilibrium crystalline positions and CO₂ molecules are trapped inside the hydrate cages, forming 4-5 hydrate layers occupied by the guest molecules. Note that there are still water molecules in the aqueous phase between the incipient forming hydrate solid phase and the CO₂-rich liquid phases located at the borders of the simulation box. Finally, at $t = 200$ ns (bottom) all water molecules are in the hydrate solid phase in coexistence with the CO₂-rich liquid phase. It will be clear later in this section that the mold used here is not appropriate to calculate interfacial energies. However, these results show that the MI method can be used to induce the formation of hydrates in the corresponding aqueous solution. The MI methodology allows to calculate the

interfacial free energy of the CO₂-hydrate-water system as a function of r_w . Although, it is necessary to determine the optimal value of r_w , denoted by r_w^0 , that gives the right value of γ_{hw} . This election is key in this technique since the uncertainty of r_w^0 is the main source of error in the calculation of the interfacial free energy [52, 60]. It is possible to select the optimal value r_w^0 from the inspection of n_h , the number of molecules of the crystalline solid slab formed when the mold is switched on.

We perform simulations in the $NP_{\varepsilon}\mathcal{AT}$ ensemble starting from the equilibrium LL initial configuration previously generated, with the mold fully switched on ($\varepsilon = \varepsilon_m$), for different values of r_w . For each selected r_w , we perform several independent trajectories to obtain a statistical picture of the behavior of the system. As we have mentioned previously, the determination of the CO₂ hydrate-water interfacial free energy using the MI technique is a much more difficult task compared with other systems [52, 60, 61], not only because one has to start from a two-phase coexisting system, but also due to the nature itself of hydrates. The formation of the solid crystalline slab involves the arrangement of water molecules around the equilibrium crystalline positions catalyzed by the mold when is switched on. Note that the sites of the mold are located in the middle of the simulation box (H₂O-rich liquid phase) and the arrangement of water molecules is usually a quick process compared with the full formation of the hydrate slab. However, the CO₂ molecules must also occupy their equilibrium positions in order to form a stable hydrate slab. Since solubility of CO₂ in H₂O at the coexistence conditions is very low, there are not enough CO₂ molecules in the H₂O-rich liquid phase to form a stable hydrate slab. Consequently, it is necessary that CO₂ molecules diffuse from the sides of the simulation box to the center of it in order a stable hydrate slab will be formed. Note that the thermodynamic stability of hydrate phases is achieved due to the presence of the guest molecules inside the hydrate crystalline structure [1]. According to this, simulation lengths considered in this work have to be much longer than in previous studies. For example, Espinosa *et al.* [52, 60] analyze the behavior of n_h for Lennard-Jones and water systems during 1 ns, approximately, whereas in this work we monitor the number of water molecules in the hydrate crystalline slab along 100 ns, two orders of magnitude larger.

According to Vega and collaborators [52, 60], if $r_w < r_w^0$, a hydrate crystalline slab should grow in all trajectories considered. In particular, evolution of trajectories with time do not show any induction period. In other words, the number of water molecules in the crystal

cluster grows very quickly, indicating that there is no free energy barrier between the fluid and the solid, and therefore the formation of the hydrate slab takes place spontaneously. Contrary, if $r_w > r_w^0$, there exists a free energy barrier between the fluid and the solid that must be overcome. This can be observed in the evolution of the number of water molecules in the crystal clusters (hydrate) with time. Some of the trajectories show an induction period before the slab grows, i.e., the number of water molecules in the crystal cluster does not grow during a time period. It is possible that some trajectories do not show slab formation, especially if the r_w values are very high compared with those of r_w^0 .

The key magnitude in the previous discussion is n_h , the number of water molecules in the crystalline slab formed when the mold is switched on. To determine this magnitude, we use the rotationally invariant local bond order parameters, \bar{q}_i , proposed by Lechner and Dellago [70] (see Eqs. (1), (5) and (6) in their work). These order parameters are similar to the well-known translational and orientational order parameters proposed by Truskett *et al.* [71] and Chau and Hardwick [72], respectively, that have been recently used by Sebastiani *et al.* [73] to characterize the “phase” of water within supramolecular tetrahedral cages. This approach or similar techniques have been previously used by several authors in the literature to identify if a molecule is a fluid-like or solid-like particle [74–78], including Espinosa and coworkers [52, 59]. In this work, we use a similar approach than Sanz *et al.* [59], that analyzed the crystallization of water molecules in ice Ih solid phase but with two important differences: (1) we use a $\bar{q}_3 - \bar{q}_6$ representation, instead of the usual $\bar{q}_4 - \bar{q}_6$ proposed by Lechner and Dellago and other authors; and (2) the cutoff distance to identify neighbors for the calculation of \bar{q}_i between the oxygen atoms was chosen in a different way.

The combination of \bar{q}_4 and \bar{q}_6 bond-order parameters does not allow to discriminate between solid-like and liquid-like molecules for systems in which stable solid phase is a hydrate [79]. In the particular case of sI hydrates, it is possible to use a threshold value $\bar{q}_{3,t} \approx 0.03$ in the $\bar{q}_3 - \bar{q}_6$ representation that separates the liquid from the hydrate as it is shown in Figure 3. This value has been obtained from the percentage of mislabeled particles as a function of the threshold value chosen for the \bar{q}_3 parameter [59]. On the other hand, Sanz *et al.* [59] used a cutoff distance for calculating the \bar{q}_i parameters of 3.5 Å, that corresponds to the position of the first minimum of the oxygen-oxygen pair correlation function in the liquid phase. However, we use a value of 5.5 Å, that corresponds to the position of the

Figure 3: Values of \bar{q}_3 and \bar{q}_6 for water molecules in a system formed by 736 water molecules and 256 CO₂ molecules at coexistence conditions (40 MPa and 278 K) corresponding to 2.5×10^7 MD steps of simulation (50 ns). Blue crosses represent water molecules in the liquid phase and red pluses to water molecules in the hydrate phase.

second minimum of the oxygen-oxygen pair correlation function in the hydrate phase. This allows, together with the $\bar{q}_3 - \bar{q}_6$ representation, to distinguish clearly between solid-like and liquid-like molecules for CO₂ hydrates.

Using this information, we have analyzed the time evolution of n_h , the number of water molecules in the CO₂ hydrate slab, for several well radius considered in this work. In particular, we have studied eighteen values ranging from 0.76 Å (0.24σ) to 1.457 Å (0.46σ), with $\sigma = 3.1668$ Å the diameter associated with the Lennard-Jones intermolecular potential of the TIP4P/ice water model [53]. Selected results for n_h , as a function of time, are shown in Figure 4. The complete set of results are presented in the SI material. As we have mentioned previously, the key point to determine r_w^0 is the identification of what Espinosa *et al.* [52] call induction period along the evolution of the number of water molecules in the crystal slab n_h , as a function of time. According to their seminal work, the induction period is the time interval observed from the beginning of a simulation from a fluid configuration ($t = 0$ ns) up to a time in which n_h starts to grow, on average, monotonically. During the induction period n_h fluctuates around its initial value. As we have already mentioned, the existence of an induction period indicates that there is a free energy barrier between the fluid and solid states that avoids the formation of a crystal slab. Contrary, the absence of such an induction period indicates that there is no free energy

Figure 4: Number of water molecules in the crystal slab, n_h , as a function of time for several trajectories and different well radius, r_w (as indicated in the legend). All simulations are performed at coexistence conditions (40 MPa and 287 K). In all cases, $\varepsilon = 8 k_B T$. Each color represents an independent trajectory generated using different seeds starting from the same fluid configuration.

barrier.

Following the work of Espinosa *et al.*, for each r_w value we have run five independent trajectories using different seeds starting from the same fluid configuration. This allows to have a statistical picture of the behavior of the system upon switching the mold on. Each trajectory is run over 100 ns. This simulation length is two orders of magnitude larger than the lengths used in the seminal work of Espinosa and coworkers to distinguish if trajectories show or not induction periods. Why? Because there exist subtle but key differences between formation of Ih ice from liquid water at coexistence conditions and the formation of CO₂ hydrates from CO₂ dissolved in water, also at coexistence conditions. In the case of the original implementation of the MI methodology, water molecules can accommodate nearly immediately in the crystallographic positions of the Ih ice structure when the mold is switched on. In the current case, the stable crystalline phase is

only formed when the guest molecules (CO₂), occupy their equilibrium positions and water molecules are rearranged around the CO₂ molecules to enclathrate them in the corresponding hydrate cages. Therefore, formation of CO₂ hydrates is dominated by thermodynamic and kinetic hindrances. The H₂O + CO₂ binary mixture exhibits LL immiscibility at thermodynamic conditions at which CO₂ hydrate is formed. The low solubility of CO₂ in water acts as thermodynamic hindrance, increasing simulation times. In addition to that, diffusion of CO₂ (from the CO₂-rich liquid phase) across the H₂O-rich liquid phase acts as kinetic hindrance, that also increases simulation times. As a consequence of this, longer simulation runs are needed to distinguish different behaviors of n_h , as a function of time, and to identify correctly possible induction periods in trajectories.

It is possible to identify three different scenarios that allow to determine with confidence the optimal value of

r_w , its uncertainty, and consequently, γ_{hw} and its error: scenario I, corresponding to low values of r_w , in which none of the trajectories exhibits induction period and system always crystallizes if simulation runs are sufficiently long (no free energy barrier between the fluid and solid phases exists); scenario II, corresponding to intermediate values of r_w , in which at least one of the independent trajectories exhibits an induction period, and after some time, the system crystallizes. In addition to that, all independent trajectories finally crystallize if the simulation runs are sufficiently long. The particular length that a given simulation must run depends on the system. Although in this case there is an energy barrier between the fluid and the solid slab, the system is able to overcome it at some point; and finally, scenario III, corresponds to large values of r_w . In this case, none of the trajectories shows, on average, monotonous increase of n_h with time. This indicates that there is a free energy barrier between the fluid and the solid high enough that does not allow the system to crystallize.

As can be seen in Figure 4 (see SI material for the rest of r_w investigated), simulations with $r_w \leq 1.172 \text{ \AA}$ (0.37σ) do not show any induction period for all the trajectories considered since n_h grows, on average, monotonically from $t \approx 0$ ns. In all cases, there is not free energy barrier between the liquid water and the solid CO_2 hydrate slab. Consequently, these simulations cannot be used for thermodynamic integration because the integration path crosses a first-order phase transition (scenario I). For simulations with $1.203 \text{ \AA} \leq r_w \leq 1.283 \text{ \AA}$ ($0.38\sigma \leq r_w \leq 0.405\sigma$), at least one trajectory shows an induction period, i.e., n_h does not grow, on average, from $t \approx 0$ ns. Particularly, different induction periods can be observed for systems with $r_w = 1.203$ (0 – 30 ns for orange and green trajectories), 1.219 (0 – 30 ns for blue trajectory and 0 – 70 ns for orange trajectory), 1.235 (0 – 10 ns for orange, 0 – 15 ns for maroon, and 0 – 20 ns for blue trajectories), 1.267 (0 – 40 ns for red, 0 – 55 ns for green, and 0 – 65 ns for orange trajectories), and 1.283 \AA (0 – 45 ns for green trajectory). The common behavior of these systems, according to scenario II, is that all trajectories exhibit, on average, a monotonous growing of n_h with time, indicating that although systems have free energy barriers between the liquid and solid phases, they are able to overcome them and crystallize if simulations are long enough. Finally, none of the simulations with $r_w \geq 1.298 \text{ \AA}$ ($r_w \geq 0.41\sigma$) exhibit, on average, monotonic increasing of n_h with time due to the existence of a free energy barrier between the fluid and solid that does not allow the system to crystallize.

According to this and following Espinosa *et al.*, r_w^0 should be between $r_w = 1.172 \text{ \AA}$ and $r_w = 1.203 \text{ \AA}$.

However, the determination of interfacial free energies of hydrates at coexistence suffers thermodynamic and kinetic hindrances that makes very difficult to distinguish the behavior of the system, as it has already been explained. Due to this and to ensure that r_w^0 and consequently γ_{hw} , are provided with appropriate uncertainties, we have chosen a more conservative confidence interval. We assume that $r_w^{(l)} = 1.140 \text{ \AA}$ is the lower bound of r_w^0 and $r_w^{(u)} = 1.235 \text{ \AA}$ its upper bound according to the mold integration method. With this election, $r_w^0 = \frac{r_w^{(l)} + r_w^{(u)}}{2} \approx 1.1875 \text{ \AA}$ the mean value of the upper and lower bounds of r_w . The uncertainty of r_w^0 is estimated as half of the distance between the $r_w^{(u)}$ and $r_w^{(l)}$, i.e., $\sigma_{r_w^0} = \frac{r_w^{(u)} - r_w^{(l)}}{2} \approx 0.0475 \text{ \AA}$. Keeping only the most significant figure for the uncertainty and rounding off appropriately, the final value of the optimal radius is $r_w^0 = 1.19(5) \text{ \AA}$.

4.2. Thermodynamic integration

Once r_w^0 is known, we determine $\gamma_{hw}(r_w)$ by means of thermodynamic integration for different values of $r_w > r_w^0$. According to the results presented in the previous section, $r_w = 1.267, 1.283,$ and 1.298 \AA are appropriate values for the determination of the CO_2 hydrate – water interfacial free energy using the MI methodology.

To calculate the integral of Eq. (2) for each potential range of interacting sites of the model, r_w , it is necessary to evaluate the average of filled wells with water molecules, $\langle N_{fw}(\varepsilon) \rangle_{NP_z\mathcal{AT}}$, at a given number of ε values. Due to the nature of the interaction potential between the sites of the mold and water molecules this is simply the total mold-water interaction energy divided by $-\varepsilon$. We have checked that accurate values of the integral are obtained using typically 15 different values of ε . Each point has been obtained switching the mold on with the corresponding well-water interaction parameter value ε and performing MD simulations in the $NP_z\mathcal{AT}$ ensemble. Simulations are equilibrated during 20 ns and $N_{fw}(\varepsilon)$, the number of filled wells, is averaged over 80 ns. Note that simulation periods used in this work are longer than those used in previous works of Espinosa *et al.* [52, 60]. This is because, as explained in the previous section, CO_2 molecules must diffuse along the whole simulation box to occupy their equilibrium positions in order to form a stable hydrate slab in the middle of the box. The number of filled wells, N_{fw} , are obtained as appropriate averages during the production period. In order to estimate errors N_{fw} , we have applied the sub-block method. The production period, 80 ns, is divided into M independent blocks. The statistical errors are then estimated from the standard deviation

Figure 5: Averaged number of filled wells, $\langle N_{fw}(\epsilon) \rangle_{NP_z\mathcal{AT}}$, as a function of the well depth ϵ , for the principal plane of the CO₂ hydrate. The radius of the mold used is 1.283 Å. All simulations are performed at 40 MPa and 287 K. The circles correspond to the value obtained from $NP_z\mathcal{AT}$ simulations with 20 ns of equilibration and 80 ns of production. The curve is included as a guide to the eye.

of the average, $\sigma_{\langle N_{fw} \rangle} = \overline{\sigma_{fw}} / \sqrt{M}$ where $\overline{\sigma_{fw}}$ is the variance of the block average and M has been fixed to $M = 10$.

As an example, Figure 5 shows the $\langle N_{fw}(\epsilon) \rangle_{NP_z\mathcal{AT}}$ behavior as a function of the well depth, ϵ , for the case $r_w = 1.283$ Å. Results corresponding to the other interaction ranges (1.267 and 1.298 Å) exhibit the same qualitative behavior that those presented here. The error bars cannot be distinguished in Figure 5 because are smaller than the symbol size. Particularly, $\sigma_{\langle N_{fw} \rangle} = 0.04$ for low values of the well depth, $\epsilon \approx k_B T$ and $\sigma_{\langle N_{fw} \rangle} = 0.03$ for high values of the well depth, $\epsilon \approx 6 - 7 k_B T$. $\langle N_{fw}(\epsilon) \rangle_{NP_z\mathcal{AT}}$ increases smoothly as the strength of the well-water interacting potential is increased. For $\epsilon = 0$, when the mold is switched off, the average number of wells occupied is 16, approximately. As $\epsilon \rightarrow \epsilon_m$ (mold fully switched on), the average number of wells occupied tends to 56, the total number of well available in the simulation box, N_w . Note that once the plateau is reached, $\langle N_{fw}(\epsilon) \rangle_{NP_z\mathcal{AT}}$, and consequently $\gamma_{hw}(r_w)$, is independent of ϵ . It is interesting to remark that the maximum ϵ value used in this work, $\epsilon = 8 k_B T$, satisfies the two main conditions that ensure the goodness of the MI methodology: (1) every well of the mold is occupied by a water molecule in the final state of the thermodynamic integration, i.e., $\langle N_{fw}(\epsilon) \rangle_{NP_z\mathcal{AT}} \rightarrow N_w$ as $\epsilon \rightarrow \epsilon_m$; and (2) the ϵ_m value chosen in this work guarantees the smoothness of the function $\langle N_{fw}(\epsilon) \rangle_{NP_z\mathcal{AT}}$. Particularly,

Figure 6: Number of water molecules in the crystal slab, n_h , as a function of time for the principal plane of the CO₂ hydrate. Different curves correspond to the well depths analyzed in Figure 5: (a) 0.04 (red), 0.08 (blue), 0.4 (green), 0.8 (magenta), and 1.2 (orange); (b) 1.6 (red), 2 (blue), 2.4 (green), 2.6 (magenta), and 3 (orange); and (c) 3.4 (red), 4 (blue), 4.8 (green), 6.4 (magenta), and $8 k_B T$ (orange). The radius of the mold used is $r_w = 1.298$ Å. All the results have been obtained using $NP_z\mathcal{AT}$ simulations at 40 MPa and 287 K.

we have checked that other values, such as $\epsilon = 6$ and even $16 k_B T$, provide identical results for interfacial energy values, providing essentially the same curve as that shown in Figure 5.

As we have previously mentioned, all thermodynamic states visited by the system during the simulations must be in the liquid phase. This ensures that the integration path to determine ΔG_m does not cross a first-order phase transition, and consequently, ΔG_m can be easily related with ΔG^{hw} , the reversible work to form the crystalline slab. This can be done monitoring the number of water molecules that belong to the hydrate slab, n_h , and checking that it does not grow indefinitely at any integration point. Figure 6 shows the evolution of n_h as a function of time for all the ϵ values analyzed for $r_w = 1.298$ Å. As can be seen, in nearly all cases n_h show a stationary value around 100-120 water molecules in the simulation box. Particularly, n_h does not grow beyond 200 water molecules, approximately. Note that we are using 56 interacting sites for the mold and the total number of water molecules used in simulations is 736, i.e., the hydrate phase does not grow irreversibly for any of the well depths and associating energies used during the thermodynamic integration ensuring the reversibility of the simulations. This indicates that there is a stable hydrate slab formed in the middle of the simulation box and two CO₂ hydrate

– water interfaces. It is interesting to note that there is an incipient and maintained crystal growing for the deepest wells, $\varepsilon = 6.4$ and $8k_B T$ corresponding to the magenta and orange curves in part (c) of Figure 6, respectively. However, these fluctuations are only maintained during 5 ns in both cases, approximately. After this time, the average number of water molecules in the hydrate crystalline phase fluctuates around 100–120 molecules. This indicates clearly that simulations for all the wells, including those for 6.4 and $8k_B T$, are performed at conditions at which thermodynamic integration can be safely performed.

4.3. Interfacial free energy

From the behavior of the averaged number of filled wells, $\langle N_{fw}(\varepsilon) \rangle_{NP, \varepsilon, AT}$, as a function of the well depth, ε , it is possible to determine the interfacial free energy of the CO₂ hydrate – water interface for a given value of the radius of the mold used to perform our calculations. In particular, for the case of $r_w = 1.267 \text{ \AA}$, we have determined a value of $\Delta G_m = -372.51 k_B T$. According to Eq. (3), one must subtract the well – oxygen associating energy to obtain the reversible work needed to form the hydrate crystalline slab, $\Delta G^{hw} = \Delta G_m + N_w \varepsilon_m = -372.51 k_B T + 56 \times 8 k_B T = 75.49 k_B T$. Using the definition of the interfacial free energy given by Eq. (1), the CO₂ hydrate interfacial energy obtained from the MI technique with $r_w = 1.267 \text{ \AA}$ is $\gamma_{hw} = 25.89 \text{ mJ/m}^2$. The same direct calculation can be done for the rest r_w values employed in this work. We obtain $\gamma_{hw} = 25.52 \text{ mJ/m}^2$ for $r_w = 1.283 \text{ \AA}$ and $\gamma_{hw} = 24.77 \text{ mJ/m}^2$ for $r_w = 1.298 \text{ \AA}$.

Following the works of Espinosa *et al.* [52, 60, 61], we have represented the γ_{hw} values obtained for three different values of $r_w > r_w^0$. Figure 7 shows the values of γ_{hw} as a function of r_w . As can be seen, data follow a linear dependence of the interfacial free energy with r_w , as in previous works. Although there is not a definite proof for this behavior, our results confirm that the interfacial free energy of the CO₂ hydrate-water interface follows the same trend (dashed blue line). According to the approach presented by Espinosa and coworkers, we perform a linear regression using the three γ_{hw} values obtained in this work and determine the interfacial free energy of the system, i.e., γ_{hw} evaluated at $r_w = r_w^0 = 1.19(5) \text{ \AA}$. From the results presented in Figure 7, the interfacial free energy is obtained as the mean value of γ_{hw} evaluated at the lower bound of r_w , $r_w^{(l)} = 1.140 \text{ \AA}$ ($\gamma_{hw}^{(l)} = 30.50 \text{ mJ/m}^2$) and the upper bound of $r_w^{(u)} = 1.235 \text{ \AA}$ ($\gamma_{hw}^{(u)} = 27.04 \text{ mJ/m}^2$), given a value $\gamma_{hw} = (\gamma_{hw}^{(l)} + \gamma_{hw}^{(u)})/2 = 28.67 \text{ mJ/m}^2$ (open red squares).

Figure 7: Interfacial free energy, as a function of the potential well radius of the mold (open blue circles). The blue dashed line represents a linear fit of the data, the open red squares the interfacial tension evaluated at $r_w^{(l)}$ and $r_w^{(u)}$, and the open green diamond the extrapolation of the linear fit to the optimal well radius.

Uncertainties associated to γ_{hw} come from two sources: errors due to the estimations of r_w^0 and uncertainties associated with the calculation of each $\langle N_{fw}(\varepsilon) \rangle$ in the integral of Eq. (2). Unfortunately, it is difficult to estimate the propagation of uncertainties to the integral defined by ΔG_m . Hence, we assume that the main error in γ_{hw} is due to the uncertainty in r_w^0 . This uncertainty is estimated as follows. Since the value of γ_{hw} is in the middle of the interval $[\gamma_{hw}^{(l)}, \gamma_{hw}^{(u)}]$, we assume the uncertainty of γ_{hw} is $\sigma_{\gamma_{hw}} = (\gamma_{hw}^{(u)} - \gamma_{hw}^{(l)})/2 \approx 1.73 \text{ mJ/m}^2$. Considering only the most significant figure for the uncertainty and rounding off appropriately, the uncertainty of γ_{hw} is $\sigma_{\gamma_{hw}} = 2 \text{ mJ/m}^2$. With this election, the final value of the interfacial free energy and its uncertainty is $\gamma_{hw} = 29(2) \text{ mJ/m}^2$ (open green diamond).

It is possible to compare the CO₂ hydrate interfacial free energy obtained by means of computer simulation with experimental data taken from the literature. According to the best of our knowledge, only Uchida *et al.* reported an interfacial free energy value $\gamma_{hw} = 28(6) \text{ mJ/m}^2$ for the CO₂ hydrate-water interface (after the correction of Anderson *et al.* explained previously). Anderson and collaborators obtained a different value, $\gamma_{hw} = 30(3) \text{ mJ/m}^2$ for the same system.

The origin of the discrepancies between the Uchida and Anderson experiments can be found in the use of different values of the magnitudes involved in the Gibbs–Thomson equation [80, 81]. Additionally, its use assumes that all pores in the porous materials are cylin-

drical, with only one and well-defined pore size, independent, and non-connected [19, 20]. Unfortunately, real mesoporous materials are far from this idyllic picture. They are made by a network of interconnected cylindrical pores with a given pore size distribution [82]. This produces a combination of “individual” experimental dissociation curves and different definitions for d , the mean pore diameter. Finally, there exists an unfrozen layer of liquid (water), of few angstroms in thickness, between the solid phase (hydrate) and the pore wall [21–24, 83–86], producing an enhancement of the interfacial free energies that is difficult to quantify and correct, and consequently the values are slightly larger than those in absence of pores.

The results obtained in this work are relevant due to several reasons. First at all, the value obtained for the hydrate-water interfacial free energy here, $\gamma_{hw} = 29(2) \text{ mJ/m}^2$, is within the experimental value measured by Uchida *et al.* [22], $\gamma_{hw} = 28(6) \text{ J/m}^2$. The experimental determination of Anderson *et al.* for the interfacial energy ranges from 27 to 33 J/m^2 . Our value is also within the boundaries provided by these authors. Note the values for γ_{hw} obtained are reliable since the same model for water (TIP4P/ice) has been recently used by Vega and coworkers to accurately determine the Ih ice-water interfacial free energy [52]. Taking into account the absence of more reliable experimental values (estimated error of Uchida’s value are around $\sim 20\%$ and those of Anderson $\sim 10\%$), and the difficulties for determining experimentally and using computational techniques SF interfacial free energies, we can conclude that agreement between computer simulation predictions and experimental data is excellent.

Not only agreement between predictions from computer simulation and experimental data taken from the literature is outstanding. From a more fundamental point of view, the estimation of the hydrate-water interfacial energy presented in this paper is only based on basic principles without the use of phenomenological theories. Particularly, the predictions are obtained from: (1) the thermodynamic definition of the interfacial free energy, i.e., as the reversible work needed to create a hydrate-water interface at coexistence; (2) the solution of the Newton’s classical equations of motion of the molecules that form the system using well-established MD techniques; and (3) the use of rotationally invariant local bond-order parameters that allow to distinguish between hydrate-like and water-like molecules during computer simulations.

This approach contrasts with other theoretical methods or even experiments themselves that use phenomenological theories or approximations. For instance, the

Seeding technique proposed by Bai and Li [87] has been recently used to determine the interfacial energy of different molecular models, including water and hydrates [48, 59]. Care must be taken with this methodology since the interfacial energy value does not correspond to the that at coexistence conditions since the technique only works at supersaturation conditions, i.e., at temperatures well below the coexistence temperature. To obtain the interfacial energy value at coexistence it is necessary to extrapolate the values obtained to the coexistence temperature. This approach uses the Classical Nucleation Theory to estimate the interfacial free energy assuming important approximations, including that the critical cluster obtained during simulation is spherical. In the case of the Uchida *et al.* and Anderson *et al.* experiments, interfacial values are indirect measurements with a number of approximations that could provoke significant uncertainties in the measurements, as it has been previously explained: all pores in silica glass are cylindrical, existence of a finite distribution of pore sizes, and use of different values for the enthalpy for hydrate dissociation and hydrate density, among other assumptions.

Finally, it is important to recall here one of the drawbacks of using porous materials to measure interfacial free energies of solids in combination with the Gibbs–Thomson relationship. As it was mentioned, it is well-known that experiments of dissociation of hydrates in porous materials involve the presence of an unfrozen layer of water, of few angstroms in thickness, between the hydrate and the pore wall [21–24, 83–86]. This provokes an enhancement of the interfacial free energies, and consequently the values measured are slightly larger than those in the bulk phase due to the presence of the pore walls. The overestimation of the interfacial free energy value obtained from this technique, with respect to that in bulk, could be around $1 - 5 \text{ mJ/m}^2$, approximately [88–92]. According to this, agreement between the predictions from simulations and values obtained by Anderson, and particularly by Uchida, is remarkable.

5. Conclusion

We have determined the CO_2 hydrate – water interfacial free energy by means of computer simulation using the TIP4P/ice and TraPPE models for water and carbon dioxide, respectively. This is the first calculation of the CO_2 hydrate interfacial energy using molecular dynamics simulations at coexistence conditions from fundamental principles, including the definition of interfacial free energy, Thermodynamics, and Statistical Mechanics.

To predict the interfacial free energy, we use an extension of the recently proposed mold integration method to deal with CO₂ hydrates. The technique is extended in several ways: (1) to deal with binary mixtures; (2) to account for two-phase equilibrium conditions in order to explicitly simulate coexistence of three phases, hydrate, aqueous solution of water and aqueous solution of carbon dioxide; and (3) to optimize rotationally invariant local bond order parameters to identify water-like and hydrate-like particles and to follow the growth of the hydrate solid phase along the simulations.

The interfacial free energy predictions obtained in this work are compared with the two only indirect experimental data existing in the literature from Uchida *et al.* [21, 22] and Anderson *et al.* [23, 24] that combined hydrate equilibrium measurements under confinement through the Gibbs-Thomson equation. Experimental data of both authors show large uncertainties compared with that of the ice–water interfacial energy value. According to the authors, both results are consistent but they should be considered as conservative estimates since depend on available physical property data, including enthalpy for hydrate dissociation and hydrate density, and the use of a phenomenological equation. The interfacial free energy obtained from simulation agrees very well with Uchida’s experimental data and slightly underestimates the Anderson’s experimental values. However, it is consistent with results of Anderson if we take into account that experimental values are enhanced due to the presence of an unfrozen layer of water between hydrates and pore walls. Simulation results can be considered as a valuable alternative method to provide reliable and confident data. Our calculations show that the mold integration methodology can be used to determine interfacial free energies of complex solid phases, including hydrates.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Jesús Algaba: Methodology, Investigation. **Esteban Acuña:** Validation, Investigation. **José Manuel Míguez:** Conceptualization, Supervision. **Bruno Mendiboure:** Investigation, Formal analysis. **Iván M. Zerón:** Writing – review & editing. **Felipe J. Blas:** Funding acquisition, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supporting Information

See Supporting Information for a general perspective of the n_h time evolution for complete set of r_w investigated.

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